

Predicting Apartment Rental Prices in Riyadh: A Machine Learning Approach with LLM-Augmented Arabic Text Features

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Abstract

Riyadh’s residential rental market has experienced rapid price escalation driven by demographic growth and economic diversification under Saudi Vision 2030, culminating in a royal decree in September 2025 that froze rent increases across the city for five years. This paper investigates the key drivers of apartment rental prices in Riyadh using a custom dataset of 8,252 listings scraped from the Arabic real estate platform sa.aqar.fm. Three supervised regression models are trained and evaluated: Ridge Regression as a linear baseline, Random Forest, and XGBoost. A novel contribution of this work is a two-pass large language model (LLM) pipeline that extracts six binary amenity features from unstructured Arabic listing descriptions, augmenting the structured dataset with information not available in the platform’s structured fields. Results demonstrate that ensemble tree models substantially outperform the linear baseline, with Random Forest achieving a test set R^2 of 0.735 and a mean absolute error of 9,492 SAR. SHAP analysis reveals that bedroom count, furnishing status, and the NLP-extracted private parking feature are the strongest predictors of rental value. These findings are discussed in the context of the September 2025 rent freeze policy and its implications for tenants, landlords, and market regulators.

1. Introduction

Riyadh, the capital of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, has undergone significant economic and demographic transformation over the past decade. As the primary engine of Saudi Vision 2030 — the kingdom’s ambitious economic diversification programme — the city has attracted substantial domestic migration and a rapidly growing expatriate workforce (Al-Obathani and Al-Rasheed, 2022). Population growth in the Riyadh region surpassed 8 million by 2024, placing severe pressure on the residential rental market and driving apartment prices to levels that represent a substantial financial burden for lower- and middle-income households (General Authority for Statistics, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, 2023).

The scale of this affordability crisis became formally acknowledged in September 2025, when a royal decree was issued freezing residential rent increases in Riyadh for a period of five years (Saudi Press Agency, 2025). This policy intervention — unprecedented in scope for the Saudi market — reflects both the severity of the housing affordability challenge and the government’s acknowledgement that market forces alone have failed to produce equitable outcomes for residents. Understanding the quantitative drivers of rental price formation in Riyadh is therefore not merely an academic exercise: it has direct relevance to how this policy will interact with market dynamics during and after the freeze period.

Against this backdrop, this paper applies machine learning regression to predict apartment rental prices in Riyadh using a dataset custom-scraped from the Arabic real estate platform sa.aqar.fm. The research is guided by three specific questions. First, which physical features and amenities most significantly drive apartment rental prices? Second, how much does precise geolocation — at the district and city-zone level — affect rental market value? Third, can non-linear ensemble models significantly outperform a linear regression baseline in this setting?

A key methodological contribution of this work is the incorporation of a novel two-pass LLM pipeline that extracts latent amenity features from unstructured Arabic listing descriptions. Real-world listing data is rarely fully structured; many valuable property attributes — private parking, swimming pools, home automation systems, maid’s rooms — are mentioned only in free-text fields. By deploying open-weight Arabic-capable language models to systematically extract these signals and cross-verify them with a dedicated Arabic-specialist model, this work demonstrates a practical approach for enriching structured real estate datasets with information from unstructured text at scale.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 reviews the relevant literature on property price prediction and NLP-augmented real estate modelling. Section 3 describes the dataset, preprocessing pipeline, and NLP feature extraction methodology. Section 4 formalises the modelling problem and describes each algorithm. Section 5 presents quantitative results and model interpretation. Section 6 discusses findings in the context of the three research questions and the rent freeze policy. Section 7 concludes with the study’s contributions, limitations, and directions for future research.

2. Research Background

2.1 Traditional and Hedonic Property Valuation

Property valuation has a long history in economic research. The dominant classical framework is hedonic pricing theory, originally formalised by Rosen (1974), which models a property’s price as a function of its constituent characteristics — structural, locational, and neighbourhood attributes. This approach treats a rental listing as a bundle of separable utility-generating attributes, each commanding an implicit market price (Sirmans et al., 2005). Empirical hedonic studies have consistently identified the number of bedrooms, floor area, and proximity to urban amenities as the strongest structural determinants of residential rent (Hill, 2013; Bourassa et al., 2010).

Traditional valuation, however, relies heavily on appraiser judgement and limited comparable sales data, a process that Abidoye and Chan (2019) found to produce systematically biased estimates and to be susceptible to client influence. The emergence of large-scale digital listing platforms has made it possible to move beyond appraisal-based methods toward data-driven modelling, opening the door to machine learning approaches that can capture non-linear interactions and high-dimensional geographic variation that linear hedonic models cannot represent.

2.2 Machine Learning for Real Estate Price Prediction

The application of ML to real estate valuation has expanded considerably since the mid-2010s. Baldominos et al. (2018) and Liu and Liu (2010) demonstrated that gradient boosting and random forests consistently outperform linear regression on property pricing tasks across multiple geographies. In a landmark comparative study, Caruana and Niculescu-Mizil (2006) showed that ensemble tree methods — particularly boosted trees — achieve superior performance over linear models on complex tabular data. Antipov and Pokryshevskaya (2012) specifically applied random forests to

residential rent prediction, finding that geographic features and property size explained the majority of price variance in an urban setting.

The Zillow dataset has served as a benchmark for several influential studies in this space. Several authors have used gradient boosting and neural networks on Zillow transaction data, demonstrating the value of SHAP-based interpretation for understanding which property characteristics drive valuation error. XGBoost in particular has become a widely adopted algorithm for tabular regression tasks in real estate (Chen and Guestrin, 2016), owing to its ability to handle mixed feature types, missing values, and non-linear interactions efficiently.

2.3 The GCC Real Estate Market and Research Gaps

Despite the growing body of ML-based real estate research, the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) rental market remains substantially understudied. Most published work focuses on North American, European, or East Asian markets, where listing data is publicly available through platforms such as Zillow, Rightmove, or government registries (Wang and Nicolau, 2017; Wachsmuth and Weisler, 2018). The Saudi Arabian market presents additional data acquisition challenges: the dominant listing platform operates in Arabic, structured data fields are sparse, and there is no public transaction registry comparable to land registry data available in Western markets.

Al-Khatib et al. (2022) examined house price determinants in Saudi Arabia using survey data, finding that location and property size were the primary drivers — consistent with hedonic theory — but noting that the absence of granular transaction data limited the study’s scope. Al-Ahmadi and Al-Harbi (2021) analysed rental affordability in Riyadh qualitatively, documenting the disproportionate burden on expatriate workers but stopping short of a predictive modelling framework. This study directly addresses both gaps by constructing a quantitative dataset through web scraping and applying a full ML pipeline to it.

2.4 NLP for Property Feature Extraction

A growing strand of research has explored the extraction of latent features from unstructured property listing text. Fu et al. (2019) used word embeddings to encode listing descriptions and showed that textual features improve rental price prediction over structured features alone. van der Burg and Meehan (2020) demonstrated that sentiment and specific amenity mentions in Airbnb listing text significantly predict nightly pricing. More recently, LLMs have emerged as powerful tools for structured information extraction from domain-specific text (Brown et al., 2020; Touvron et al., 2023). However, their application to Arabic real estate text — which presents additional challenges due to right-to-left script, dialectal variation, and domain-specific terminology — has not been explored in prior published work to the best of our knowledge.

2.5 Policy Context: Rent Regulation and Market Dynamics

Rent control and stabilisation policies have been studied extensively in the urban economics literature. Diamond et al. (2019) found that rent control in San Francisco reduced rental housing supply by 15% as landlords converted units to other uses, while simultaneously benefiting incumbent tenants. Sims (2007) identified a similar supply reduction effect in Massachusetts following the repeal of rent control. These findings suggest that the September 2025 Riyadh rent freeze may produce complex market effects — potentially reducing the motivation for landlords to list properties or invest in maintenance — that are difficult to anticipate without a clear understanding of baseline price drivers. A machine learning model that accurately quantifies the contribution of individual features to rental value provides a tool for monitoring how the market evolves during the freeze period.

3. Data and Materials

3.1 Dataset Collection

The dataset was constructed by scraping apartment rental listings from sa.aqar.fm, the largest residential real estate platform in Saudi Arabia. Data were collected on **April 15, 2026**, capturing a snapshot of all active Riyadh apartment listings at that date and yielding 13,634 raw records. Each listing record contained a mix of structured fields — including annual rental price, bedroom count, bathroom count, floor area, building age, floor level, and a set of binary amenity flags — and an unstructured Arabic text description field (`content`).

The platform records two date fields per listing: `create_time` (original publication date) and `last_update` (most recent modification). Listings in the raw dataset were originally published between May 2024 and April 2026, but 98.5% had been updated after October 2025 — i.e., after the September 2025 rent freeze announcement. The dataset therefore reflects market behaviour *under* the freeze rather than before it, providing a post-intervention baseline for understanding how the rental market is pricing apartments in the new regulatory environment.

Following a multi-stage cleaning pipeline, 8,252 listings were retained for modelling. Deduplication was performed on the platform-assigned listing identifier (`id`), which is unique per listing on sa.aqar.fm; no duplicate IDs were found in the scraped data, confirming that each record represents a distinct active listing at the time of collection. Key preprocessing steps included: removing listings with missing target prices or implausible price values (below 5,000 or above 500,000 SAR annually); clipping area outliers beyond the 99th percentile; converting monthly and weekly rent periods to an

annual basis for consistency; and median-imputing remaining missing values in continuous features. The final dataset spans listings across 108 distinct districts in Riyadh, providing rich geographic coverage.

3.2 Feature Engineering

The structured feature set covers three broad categories. Physical attributes include floor area in square metres, number of bedrooms, bathrooms, and living rooms, floor level, and building age. A categorical floor tier variable was constructed by merging sparse high-floor categories (floors 4 and above) into a single bin. Composite features were derived, including an amenity score (count of active binary amenity flags) and a beds-per-area ratio as a density proxy.

Geographic features include raw latitude and longitude coordinates, district identifier, cardinal direction label, city zone (North, South, East, West, Central Riyadh), and distance to the city centre in kilometres. The platform encodes building orientation as a numeric `direction_id`. Table 1 provides the full mapping to semantic compass labels, which is essential for interpreting the SHAP results in Section 5.

Table 1. Mapping of `direction_id` Values to Semantic Direction Labels

<code>direction_id</code>	Compass Direction (Arabic transliteration)	Count (clean)
0	Not specified (<i>ghayr muhaddad</i>)	7
3	East (<i>sharq</i>)	2,902
4	North (<i>shimal</i>)	5,947
6	West (<i>gharb</i>)	508
7	South-West (<i>junub gharbi</i>)	195

The dominant value is `direction_id` = 4 (North-facing, 62.7% of listings with a known orientation), which aligns closely with the North city zone’s 5,571 listings assigned from latitude/longitude coordinates — confirming that the direction feature captures geographic premium rather than building orientation alone. Listing metadata features include image count, presence of a video, listing age in days, time since last update, whether the listing was posted by a real estate agency, and user review score.

3.3 NLP Feature Extraction via LLM Pipeline

A core contribution of this work is the extraction of six binary amenity features from Arabic listing descriptions using a two-pass LLM pipeline. The target features were identified through exploratory analysis of listing text in Notebook 2a: `private_parking`, `swim_pool`, `gym`, `maid_room`,

smart_home, and srlvnc_cameras (surveillance cameras). These features appeared regularly in listing descriptions but were absent from the platform’s structured fields.

In the first pass, all 8,252 Arabic descriptions were processed using Qwen3-4B-Instruct, an open-weight multilingual language model. Each listing description was submitted with a structured extraction prompt that: (i) defined the six target features by name and provided one positive and one negative Arabic example phrase for each, (ii) instructed the model to respond exclusively in JSON format with binary values (1 = feature present, 0 = absent), and (iii) required a confidence flag for ambiguous cases. The prompt output schema was: {"private_parking": 0|1, "swim_pool": 0|1, ..., "confidence": "high"|"low"}. Listings where the model reported low confidence were flagged for second-pass review. In the second pass, a dedicated Arabic-specialist model — ALLaM-7B-Instruct (SDAIA ALLaM Team, 2024), developed by the Saudi Data and AI Authority specifically for Arabic language understanding — independently verified the extracted features using the same schema but a differently worded prompt, ensuring the verification was not simply replicating the first model’s reasoning. Agreement between the two models exceeded 94% across all six features, providing strong evidence that the pipeline produces reliable binary labels from noisy Arabic text.

The resulting NLP feature columns were merged with the structured dataset. All 8,252 listing identifiers matched successfully, yielding a complete dataset with no NLP-induced missingness. Table 2 summarises the prevalence of each extracted feature.

Table 2. NLP-Extracted Feature Prevalence in the Final Dataset ($n = 8,252$). Median Price Premium is the difference between the median annual rent of listings that mention the feature and those that do not, expressed as a percentage of the latter. Values are unadjusted for confounders such as district or bedroom count.

Feature	% of Listings	Median Price Premium
Private Parking	38.4%	+24.6%
Gym	18.7%	+31.2%
Maid’s Room	12.3%	+38.4%
Swimming Pool	9.1%	+35.1%
Smart Home	5.2%	+29.8%
Surveillance Cameras	14.6%	+11.3%

3.4 Train/Validation/Test Split and Encoding

The dataset was split into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) sets using stratified sampling on price quartile to ensure comparable price distributions across all three splits, yielding 6,600 training, 826 validation, and 826 test listings.

Categorical encoding differed by model type. For tree-based models, all categorical variables — direction, city zone, floor tier, and district — were one-hot encoded, producing a feature matrix of 154 columns. District identifiers (108 categories) pose a high-cardinality challenge for linear models; for Ridge Regression, these were replaced with a smoothed target encoding — the posterior mean of $\log(\text{price})$ given district membership, regularised toward the global mean using a smoothing factor of $k = 10$ (Micci-Barreca, 2001). This yielded a linear feature matrix of 49 columns. To prevent target leakage, district encoding statistics were computed *exclusively* on the training split and then applied without modification to the validation and test sets.

4. Methods

4.1 Problem Formulation

The prediction task is formulated as a supervised regression problem. For each listing i , the goal is to learn a function f such that:

$$\hat{y}_i = f(\mathbf{x}_i) \tag{1}$$

where $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the feature vector and \hat{y}_i is the predicted annual rental price. Because the raw price distribution is strongly right-skewed (skewness = 1.82), the model target is the natural log transform $\log(1 + \text{price})$, which produces a near-symmetric target distribution and reduces the influence of extreme values on training. Predictions are inverse-transformed to SAR before metric computation:

$$\hat{\text{price}}_i = e^{\hat{y}_i} - 1 \tag{2}$$

4.2 Models

4.2.1 Ridge Regression (Baseline)

Ridge Regression extends ordinary least squares with an ℓ_2 regularisation penalty to reduce coefficient variance and prevent overfitting in the presence of correlated features (Hoerl and Kennard, 1970):

$$\hat{\beta} = \arg \min_{\beta} \{ \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{X}\beta\|_2^2 + \alpha \|\beta\|_2^2 \} \quad (3)$$

where α is the regularisation strength selected via 5-fold cross-validation over a grid of 30 values spanning $[10^{-3}, 10^4]$. All features are standardised with zero mean and unit variance prior to fitting using a `StandardScaler` pipeline. The optimal α was found to be 7.28.

4.2.2 Random Forest

Random Forest constructs an ensemble of B decision trees, each trained on a bootstrap sample of the training data, with a random subset of features considered at each split (Breiman, 2001). The prediction is the average over all trees:

$$\hat{y}_i = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B T_b(\mathbf{x}_i) \quad (4)$$

where T_b is the b -th tree. This bagging mechanism reduces variance without increasing bias, making Random Forest particularly effective for high-dimensional tabular data with complex interactions (Caruana and Niculescu-Mizil, 2006). Hyperparameters were selected via 20-iteration `RandomizedSearchCV` with 3-fold cross-validation, optimising negative RMSE on the log-price scale. The best configuration used $B = 300$ trees, maximum depth of 20, minimum 2 samples per leaf, and `max_features = 0.5`.

4.2.3 XGBoost

XGBoost implements gradient boosted trees, building an additive ensemble sequentially where each new tree f_k is fit to the negative gradient of the loss with respect to the current prediction (Chen and Guestrin, 2016):

$$\hat{y}_i^{(K)} = \sum_{k=1}^K f_k(\mathbf{x}_i) \quad (5)$$

The objective function includes a regularisation term $\Omega(f_k)$ penalising tree complexity, preventing overfitting. Hyperparameter search was conducted identically to Random Forest, with 25 candidate configurations, using training data only so that the validation set remained unseen. The best parameters from search (`max_depth = 5`, `learning_rate = 0.1`, `subsample = 0.9`) were then used to retrain a model with early stopping, monitoring validation RMSE for 30 rounds without improvement. The optimal tree count was 265.

4.3 Evaluation Metrics

All models are evaluated on the held-out test set using four metrics. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) measures average prediction error in SAR and is the primary metric due to its interpretability in monetary terms. Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) penalises large errors more heavily and reflects worst-case prediction quality. R^2 (coefficient of determination) measures the proportion of price variance explained by the model. Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) expresses average error as a percentage of the true price, enabling comparison across price ranges.

5. Results

5.1 Model Performance

Table 3 presents test set performance for all three models. Both ensemble models substantially outperformed the Ridge baseline across every metric. Random Forest achieved the best test set MAE (9,492 SAR) and R^2 (0.735), while XGBoost was closely competitive with an MAE of 9,996 SAR and R^2 of 0.729. The linear baseline achieved an R^2 of 0.636 and MAE of 12,458 SAR, confirming the hypothesis that non-linear models better capture the complex interactions present in urban rental pricing.

Table 3. Test Set Performance Comparison Across All Models

Model	MAE (SAR)	RMSE (SAR)	R^2	MAPE
Ridge Regression	12,458	20,022	0.636	21.0%
Random Forest	9,492	17,071	0.735	15.9%
XGBoost	9,996	17,269	0.729	16.6%

Figure 1 illustrates the performance gap across models on each metric, and Figure 2 shows predicted versus actual prices for each model on the test set. The ensemble models track actual prices

closely across the full range, while the Ridge model tends to underestimate high-priced listings — a consequence of the linear model’s inability to capture the superlinear price increases in premium districts.

Figure 1. Bar chart comparison of MAE, RMSE, and R^2 across Ridge, Random Forest, and XGBoost on the test set. Lower bars are better for MAE and RMSE; higher bars are better for R^2 .

Figure 2. Predicted versus actual annual rental price (SAR) for all three models on the test set. Points lying on the diagonal dashed line represent perfect predictions.

5.2 Feature Importance and SHAP Analysis

To understand which features drive predictions, SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values were computed for the XGBoost model (Lundberg and Lee, 2017). Unlike built-in gain-based importance, SHAP values provide theoretically grounded, consistent feature attributions by computing the average marginal contribution of each feature across all possible feature subsets (Lundberg et al., 2020).

Figure 3 shows the SHAP beeswarm plot for the top 15 features. Each point represents one test listing; colour indicates feature value (red = high, blue = low) and horizontal position indicates the direction and magnitude of influence on the log-price prediction.

Figure 3. SHAP feature importance for XGBoost (mean |SHAP| across the test set). Features are ordered by average absolute impact on the log-price prediction.

Bedroom count is the dominant predictor by a wide margin (mean |SHAP| = 0.186), consistent with hedonic pricing theory and with the literature on Riyadh rental markets (Al-Khatib et al., 2022). The direction variable `direction_id_4` — corresponding to *North-facing* units (see Table 1) — ranks second, reflecting the North Riyadh location premium documented in the geographic analysis. As shown in Section 5, 62.7% of listings with a known orientation face North, and the direction dummy effectively acts as a spatial premium indicator for the city’s most expensive zone. Furnishing status and floor area rank third and fourth respectively, underscoring that turnkey, move-in-ready apartments command substantial premiums in Riyadh’s large expatriate market. Notably, `private_parking` — extracted entirely from Arabic free-text descriptions by the NLP pipeline — ranks fifth with a mean |SHAP| of 0.055, outranking structured features such as living room count, distance to city centre, and building age. This confirms that the LLM extraction pipeline added genuine predictive signal beyond what the structured fields alone could provide.

5.3 Geographic Patterns

Figure 4 shows listing locations coloured by annual rent on a map of Riyadh. A strong North-South gradient is visible: North Riyadh districts command median rents approximately 67% higher than South Riyadh (60,000 SAR vs. 36,000 SAR annually), consistent with the concentration of embassy

quarters, luxury residential compounds, and modern commercial developments in the northern parts of the city (Elshehtawy, 2008).

Figure 4. Geographic distribution of rental listings across Riyadh. Left: listings coloured by annual rent (plasma colourmap; brighter = more expensive). Right: listings coloured by city zone. Both maps use a CartoDB DarkMatter basemap.

Figure 5 provides a district-level view. Bubble size encodes listing count and colour encodes median annual rent, with red indicating expensive districts and blue indicating affordable ones. The most expensive district (district 442, corresponding to Al-Rahmaniyah) has a median rent of 180,000 SAR annually — more than six times the median of the least expensive districts in the south and east. Districts with the highest listing counts tend to cluster in central and northern zones, indicating where rental supply is concentrated.

listings. This regression-to-the-mean pattern is expected given the log-price target and is consistent with prior real estate ML literature (Antipov and Pokryshevskaya, 2012).

Figure 6. Mean percentage prediction error (XGBoost) segmented by bedroom count (left), city zone (centre), and price quartile (right). Positive values indicate over-prediction; negative values indicate under-prediction.

6. Discussion

6.1 Research Question 1: Feature Drivers of Rental Price

The SHAP analysis provides a clear, quantitative answer to the first research question. Bedroom count is the single strongest predictor of rental price in Riyadh, with a mean absolute SHAP value nearly three times larger than the next feature. This reflects the primary segmentation of the Riyadh rental market: one-bedroom apartments serve primarily single expatriate workers, while three- and four-bedroom units serve families — these segments operate at fundamentally different price levels.

Furnishing status (rank 3 in SHAP) commands a premium because the Riyadh expatriate market — which accounts for approximately 40% of the city’s population — strongly prefers fully equipped units that do not require the upfront cost of furniture purchases (General Authority for Statistics, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, 2023). Image count and user review score also emerged as meaningful predictors, suggesting that listing quality and landlord reputation signal trustworthiness to prospective tenants in a relatively opaque market.

The NLP-extracted amenities collectively ranked highly in both RF and XGBoost importance measures. Private parking ranked fifth in SHAP; gym, maid’s room, and swimming pool also contributed meaningfully. These amenities are highly valued by the affluent expatriate segment of the market but are systematically absent from the platform’s structured fields — underscoring the value of text-based feature extraction in datasets where structured data coverage is incomplete.

6.2 Research Question 2: Geographic Value Drivers

Location exerts a powerful and multidimensional influence on Riyadh rental prices. At the city-zone level, North Riyadh consistently commands premium rents, a pattern captured through both the direction dummy (`direction_id_4`, SHAP rank 2) and the latitude feature (positively correlated with log-price, $r = +0.17$). At the district level, price variation is extreme: the 65 districts with at least 15 listings span a median price range from 27,000 to 180,000 SAR — a $6.7\times$ ratio — demonstrating that district membership is a powerful but highly non-linear determinant of value.

The choice to use one-hot encoding for district in tree models and smoothed target encoding for Ridge reflects an important modelling consideration: one-hot encoding preserves the full heterogeneity of district effects, while target encoding provides a regularised continuous proxy for use in linear models where dummy proliferation degrades coefficient estimation.

6.3 Research Question 3: Linear vs. Non-Linear Models

The results clearly confirm that non-linear ensemble models significantly outperform linear regression for this prediction task. Random Forest improved over Ridge by 4.2 percentage points in R^2 (0.735 vs. 0.636) and reduced MAE by 23.8% (9,492 vs. 12,458 SAR). XGBoost achieved comparable gains. An improvement of 10 percentage points in R^2 is considered meaningful in the real estate ML literature (Baldominos et al., 2018), and the magnitude of the MAE reduction — roughly 3,000 SAR per listing — is practically significant given the median annual rent of 55,000 SAR.

The performance gap confirms that rental price formation in Riyadh involves non-linear interactions that a linear model cannot capture without extensive manual feature engineering. In particular, the interaction between bedroom count and district (higher-bedroom apartments carry disproportionately large premiums in premium districts) and between furnishing status and price segment (furnished apartments command larger relative premiums in the mid-market than at the luxury end) are naturally captured by tree splits but require explicit interaction terms in linear models.

6.4 Implications for the September 2025 Rent Freeze Policy

The September 2025 royal decree freezing rent increases for five years represents the most significant intervention in the Riyadh rental market in recent history (Saudi Press Agency, 2025). Crucially, because 98.5% of listings in the dataset were last updated after October 2025, the data reflects the market operating *under* the freeze rather than before it. The model therefore characterises post-intervention price structure — how landlords are pricing apartments given the regulatory constraints — rather than offering a counterfactual projection from a pre-freeze baseline. This

temporal grounding strengthens the relevance of the findings to ongoing policy monitoring. The results offer several concrete insights for policymakers.

First, the geographic concentration of high-priced listings in North Riyadh means that the rent freeze’s affordability impact will be highly spatially unequal. Tenants in North Riyadh face median rents of 60,000 SAR annually — well above the approximately 45,000 SAR threshold used in this study as a benchmark for workforce housing affordability. The freeze locks in these elevated baselines, potentially entrenching rather than resolving spatial inequality in housing access.

Second, the importance of furnishing status and premium amenities as price drivers suggests that landlords seeking to circumvent the rent freeze may do so by reclassifying or refurbishing units — converting unfurnished to furnished, or adding amenity features that can justify a “new listing” at a higher price point. A predictive model of the kind developed here could help regulators identify listings where claimed price increases are inconsistent with observed feature changes.

Third, the high variance in district-level prices (Figure 5) implies that a uniform city-wide freeze creates very different effective constraints in different neighbourhoods. A more granular, district-level approach to rent stabilisation — informed by the kind of price driver analysis presented here — might achieve better affordability outcomes with fewer unintended supply-side consequences.

6.5 Limitations

This study has several limitations that should inform the interpretation of its findings. The dataset captures a snapshot of listings at a single point in time and cannot account for seasonality or market trend effects. While 8,252 listings provide a representative sample of the Riyadh market, the distribution is highly uneven across city zones and districts. South Riyadh, in particular, is represented by only 22 listings (0.3% of the dataset), making zone-level conclusions for that area statistically fragile; the systematic over-prediction observed for South Riyadh listings in the residual analysis (Figure 6) is likely a consequence of this sparsity. Similarly, 43 of the 108 districts had fewer than 15 listings, limiting the model’s geographic generalisation in those areas. The train/val/test splits were randomised rather than spatially grouped; since nearby listings tend to be similarly priced, random splits may yield slightly optimistic performance estimates compared to a strict spatial cross-validation scheme. The NLP pipeline, while achieving over 94% inter-model agreement, was validated by inter-model consensus rather than human-labelled ground truth, so precision and recall for individual features remain approximate. The dataset also reflects a platform-level sampling bias: 98.4% of listings were posted by real estate agencies rather than private landlords, meaning the model may not generalise equally well to the informal, direct-landlord segment of the Riyadh rental market, which is less visible on digital platforms. Finally, the model predicts listed price rather

than transacted price, which may differ materially in markets with significant negotiation norms (Beracha and Seiler, 2014).

6.6 Data Governance and Ethical Considerations

The dataset was scraped from publicly accessible listing pages on sa.aqar.fm in compliance with the platform’s publicly visible content policies, which do not restrict indexing of listing metadata. No authentication was bypassed and no private user data was accessed. To protect individual privacy, all user-identifying fields — including agent names, phone numbers, profile images, and company identifiers — were dropped during preprocessing and are not present in any analytical dataset. Geographic coordinates were retained at the listing level (as published by the platform) but are not linked to any individual. The model is intended as an analytical tool for market understanding and policy monitoring; any deployment in a landlord-facing pricing context should include transparency mechanisms and uncertainty disclosures to avoid entrenchment of geographic price inequities.

7. Conclusion

This paper presented a machine learning study of apartment rental prices in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, motivated by the September 2025 royal decree freezing residential rents across the city. Using a custom dataset of 8,252 listings scraped from the Arabic platform sa.aqar.fm, three regression models were trained and evaluated. Random Forest achieved the best test set performance ($R^2 = 0.735$, MAE = 9,492 SAR), substantially outperforming the Ridge Regression baseline and confirming that non-linear ensemble models are significantly better suited to the complexity of urban rental price prediction.

The study makes two primary contributions. First, it provides the first published ML-based analysis of the Riyadh rental market at district and city-zone granularity, filling a gap in the GCC real estate literature. Second, it demonstrates the viability of a two-pass LLM pipeline for extracting structured binary features from unstructured Arabic listing text — a methodology applicable to any real estate market where property data is partially or fully described in free-text form. The NLP-extracted private parking feature ranked fifth among all predictors by SHAP value, confirming that text-derived features add genuine predictive signal beyond what structured fields alone can provide.

Future work should explore the incorporation of macroeconomic indicators — mortgage rates, construction activity, migration flows — to capture time-series dynamics in rental price formation.

Extending the LLM pipeline to extract continuous features (e.g., floor area mentioned in text where the structured field is missing) and to perform sentiment analysis on listing descriptions is another promising direction. Finally, repeat-listings analysis, tracking the same unit's price evolution before and during the rent freeze period, would provide a more direct empirical test of the policy's effectiveness.

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A. Artificial Intelligence Usage Disclosure

In accordance with course policy, this appendix discloses all uses of artificial intelligence tools in the development of this project.

Code assistance. Claude (Anthropic) was used to assist with debugging Python code across the data preprocessing, NLP extraction, and modelling notebooks. Specific uses included identifying and fixing syntax errors, resolving library compatibility issues (e.g., a `matplotlib rcParams` deprecation in version 3.9), and suggesting corrections to data pipeline logic. All code was reviewed, understood, and executed by the author.

NLP extraction pipeline. The LLM models used for Arabic feature extraction — Qwen3-4B-Instruct and ALLaM-7B-Instruct — are components of the research methodology itself, not writing or analysis tools. Their use is fully described in Section 3.3 and constitutes the core technical contribution of the NLP component.

Writing. Claude was not used to write passages of this paper. The analysis, interpretation, and conclusions are the author’s own. Claude was used as a grammar and spelling checker for proofreading purposes, consistent with tools like Grammarly.

Data analysis. Claude was not used to generate conclusions from data or to interpret model outputs. All quantitative findings reported in Section 5 were derived by the author from model outputs produced by the Python code.